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Učinek elektro-magnetnega polja majhnih frekvenc na izdelavo in lastnosti aluminijeve zlitine 6060, ulite v kokilo z neposrednim hlajenjem

Effect of Use of Low-Frequency Electromagnetic Field on the Production and Properties of Direct Chill Cast 6060 Aluminum Alloy

Izvešček

Prispevek opisuje raziskavo učinka elektro-magnetnih polj majhnih frekvenc med navpičnim polkontinuirnim litjem drogov iz aluminijeve zlitine 6060. Dobljene rezultate smo primerjali z rezultati klasičnega polkontinuirnega litja. Primerjava je pokazala, da ima ulivanje v elektro-magnetnem polju majhnih frekvenc številne prednosti, kot gladko površino drogov, drobnejša zrna po prerezu, drobnejšo mikrostrukturo in enakomerno porazdelitev intermetalnih faz v zlitini ob enakih ali celo rahlo boljših mehanskih lastnostih. Zato uporaba takega postopka litja predstavlja možnost za ekonomske prihranke.

Ključne besede: *elektromagnetno nizkofrekvenčno litje, kokilno litje z neposrednim hlajenjem, aluminijeva zlitina, mikrostruktura, mehanske lastnosti*

Abstract

In this study, the effect of low frequency electromagnetic fields during the vertical semi-continuous casting process of 6060 aluminum alloy billets was investigated. The results were compared with those obtained by conventional semi-continuous casting. Based on comparative analysis of the results, it was found that casting in a low frequency electromagnetic field offers many advantages, such as smooth surface of the billets, smaller grain size in the cross section, finer microstructure and a uniform distribution of inter-metallic phases in the alloy, with the same or even slightly better mechanical properties. For these reasons, the employment of this casting process is considered an option for obtaining economic savings.

Keywords: low frequency electromagnetic casting process (LFEC), direct chill casting process (DC), aluminum alloy, microstructure, mechanical properties

1 UVOD IN OZADJE

Velik odstotek svetovne porabe aluminijevih

1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

tem sistemu se več drogov istočasno uliva v vodno hlajene aluminijaste kokile, ki so pritrjene na livni plošči iz nerjavnega jekla, medtem ko se dna s slepimi drogovi pogrezajo. Napake, ki se pri tem načinu litja pojavljajo, so nehomogena mikrostruktura (v mikrostrukturi so ločeni delci), razpoke na zunanjih stenah ulitih drogov, težave pri ločevanju kokile (kristalizatorja) in zaradi tega groba površina ulitih drogov. Te pomanjkljivosti so obravnavale številne študije. Zato so v zadnjem času vpeljali neposredno hlajeno kokilno litje z različnimi posebnostmi, ki močno izboljšujejo kakovost ulitih izdelkov. Ena od učinkovitih rešitev je polkontinuirno ulivanje v nizkofrekvenčnem magnetnem polju.

Ideja o ulivanju aluminijevih zlitin v magnetnem polju je znana že nekaj časa [1-5]. Raziskave o uporabi te metode v industrijskih razmerah so med drugimi delali tudi kitajski strokovnjaki in te so objavljene v številnih njihovih člankih [6-10]. Večina študij je bila posvečena učinkom elektro-magnetnih polj na ulivanje aluminijevih zlitin vrst 2xxx, 4xxx in 7xxx. Cilj te raziskave je bilo ugotavljanje učinkov uporabe elektromagnetnega nizkofrekvenčnega litja (LFEC) pri izdelavi drogov iz zlitin vrste Al-6xxx ali zlitine EN-AW-6060, kar se do sedaj še ni raziskovalo. Podobno se je ugotavljala možnost občutnega skrajšanja homogenizacijskega žarjenja, ki je neizogiben tehnološki proces pri izdelavi drogov iz teh zlitin.

Homogenizacijska toplotna obdelava drogov iz zlitine AW6000 se splošno uporablja kot primerna priprava na iztiskovanje. Eden od ciljev te obdelave je doseči fazno transformacijo faze AlFeSi. Med tem procesom se trda, krhka, monoklinska

is performed principally (DC) casting process several billets are simultaneously an aluminum mold and are fixed in a cast stainless steel, while the initial pieces is moved that occur with this type inhomogeneous microstructure separate particles with appearance of cracks on the cast billets and slant separation of the mold-related rough surface of. Such deficiencies have in a number of studies procedures with many have been introduced to of the production to a high most effective solutions casting in a low frequency field.

The idea of casting an electromagnetic field for some time [1-5]. of possible application conditions, among other Chinese scholars in studies [6-10]. Most of dedicated to the effects fields in casting aluminum 2xxx, 4xxx and 7xxx the present investigation effects of the implemented process in the development of Al-6xxx series alloy 6060, which has not hit. Similarly, the possibility shortening the time for annealing, as an inevitable process in the manufacturing

Ploščičasti delci β lahko povzročajo začetek lokalnih razpok in povzročajo površinske napake pri iztiskovanih izdelkih.

Meni se tudi, da povzročajo lokalno lepljenje in zato so v veliki meri odgovorni za slabo končno površino [15]. Zato je homogenizacija ključnega pomena za pretvorbo delcev β v fazo α -Al_x(Fe,Mn)_xSi, ki se lažje preoblikuje.

Magnezij in silicij tvorita topno fazo Mg₂Si. Med homogenizacijo gresta raztopljena Mg in Si v trdno raztopino α -Al, ki predstavlja osnovo in se prerazporedita. Če se po homogenizaciji uporabi hitro ohlajanje, se Mg in Si zadržita v trdni raztopini in tako povečata odpor za deformacijo. Zato je željeno, da nastane nekaj Mg₂Si izločkov, če so dovolj majhni, da se ponovno raztopijo med predgrevanjem in iztiskovanjem [16]. Mehanske lastnosti so v veliki meri odvisne od sposobnosti te faze, da se med iztiskovanjem raztopi in potem znova izloči.

Med strjevanjem se pri postopku litja z neposrednim hlajenjem (DC casting) železo zaradi svoje majhne topnosti v aluminiju izloča v meddendritskih prostorih. Veže se z Al, Si in včasih Mn ter tvori intermetalne delce na mejah kristalnih zrn [17]. Poleg izločkov obstaja tudi območje brez topljenca, kjer ni Mg₂Si izločkov [18]. Železove intermetalne spojine so stabilne celo pri visokih temperaturah in to vpliva na sposobnost iztiskovanja materiala [19].

2 EKSPERIMENTALNI DEL

Za te poskuse se je uporabila aluminijeva zlitina EN AW 6060. Njeno kemično sestavo prikazuje razpredelnica 1. Ta zlitina je dobro poznana in široko uporabljena

of the aims of this treatment is to achieve a phase transformation in the occurring AlFeSi phases. During this process, the hard, brittle, monoclinic eutectic β -AlFeSi phase transforms to more globular, cubic α -AlFeSi phases.

The β -phase is reported to have a negative impact on the extrudability [11-14]. The plate-like β -particles can lead to local crack initiation and induce surface defects on the extruded material.

It is also thought to cause local pick-up, and therefore it is largely responsible for a poor surface finish [15]. Therefore, homogenization is crucial to transform the β -particles into the more workable α -Al_x(Fe,Mn)_xSi phase.

Magnesium and silicon form a soluble Mg₂Si phase. During homogenization, the soluble Mg and Si enter into a solid solution in the α -aluminum matrix and are redistributed. If a fast cooling rate is employed after homogenization, the Mg and Si elements will be retained in the solid solution, thus increasing the resistance to deformation. Therefore, it may be desirable to have some Mg₂Si precipitates, provided that they are small enough to redissolve during preheating and extrusion [16]. The mechanical properties of the material depend largely on the ability of this phase to go into solution during extrusion and to precipitate afterwards.

During solidification in the DC casting process, iron segregates to the interdendritic regions because of its low solubility in aluminum. It combines with Al, Si and sometimes with Mn to form intermetallic particles at the grain boundaries [17]. Adjacent to the particles, there is a solute-depleted zone, where no Mg₂Si precipitates

Rezpredelnica 1. Kemična setava aluminijeve zlitine EN AW 6060

Table 1. Chemical composition of EN AW 6060 alloy (wt%)

Element	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Cr
Content	0.43	0.18	0.09	0.08	0.51	0.04

peči. Aluminij za ulivanje je vedno vseboval določeno količino nečistoč: vodik, alkalijske kovine, alkalijske soli in druge intermetalne vključke, ki imajo škodljiv vpliv na kakovost drogov. Te nečistoče so se odstranjevale s klasičnimi postopki obdelave taline (čiščenje, razplinjanje in modificiranje). Argon se je uporabil za razplinjenje. Pred filtracijo v livnem kanalu se je dodal kompleks TiB (aluminijeva predzlitina s 5 % modifikatorja) kot žica. Dodajanje in krmiljenje litja je bilo z avtomatom. Dodajanje žice se je krmilo s spreminjanjem hitrosti vrtenja elektromotorjev dodajalnika s sodobnim servomotorjem, priključenim na posamezen SCADA za nadzor procesa litja. Količina dodane žice pri nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem litju je bila 0,05 % mase ulitka, medtem ko je ta količina pri klasičnem kokilnem litju z neposrednim hlajenjem 0,19 %.

Oba procesa litja sta potekala pri industrijskih razmerah v tovarni "DERAL" Manerbiro (BS), Italija. Za ulivanje vzorcev med nizkofrekvenčnim elektromagnetnim ulivanjem se je uporabila livna naprava vrste ELING LP-05 (sliki 1, 2). Po vstopu se je talina razporedila po plošči v keramične kanale, najprej v sredino, potem pa ločeno v posamezne kristalizatorje.

Vroča glava na kristalizatorjih je bila tudi narejena iz keramike in je imela vlogo zadrževanja taline pri konstantni temperaturi.

Vroča glava sedi na grafitnem

2. Experimental proced

The aluminum alloy [AlMgSi0.5] was used for experiments. The chemical composition of the alloy is given in table 1. This alloy is known for its widespread use in civil engineering, as it is resistant to corrosion.

A gas furnace was used for the preparation of liquid metal. The aluminum alloy contains a certain amount of hydrogen, alkali metals, and other intermetallic inclusions, which have a detrimental effect on the mechanical properties of the billets. Removal of these impurities was performed by the standard procedure of the preparation of a liquid metal: degassing and modification. Argon was used for degassing. Prior to casting, TiB was added in the form of a pre-alloy with 5% content of TiB. The addition and control of the TiB was realized by changing the speed of electric motors in the casting process. This was performed with a modern servomotor connected to a single SCADA system. The TiB was added in the form of a pre-alloy with 5% content of TiB. The addition and control of the TiB was realized by changing the speed of electric motors in the casting process. This was performed with a modern servomotor connected to a single SCADA system. The TiB was added in the form of a pre-alloy with 5% content of TiB. The addition and control of the TiB was realized by changing the speed of electric motors in the casting process. This was performed with a modern servomotor connected to a single SCADA system.

aluminija in imajo na zgornjem delu, kjer je najtesnejši stik s talino, vstavljen grafitni obroč, da prepreči lokalno lepljenje materiala in tako pozitivno vpliva na kakovost površine drogov.

Kristalizator je iz enega kosa, njegova zunanja površina se hladi preko stika, proti izhodu pa so na robu odprtine, skozi katere teče voda, ki hladi tako kristalizator kot drog.

Elektromagnetno polje se ustvarja okoli kokile na ravni grafitnega obroča (slika 2). Med obratovanjem je livna plošča iz nerjavnega jekla popolnoma napolnjena z vodo pod tlakom okoli 2,5-5 bar. Plošča ima samo en priključek na zunanji strani za vtok, voda se porazdeli znotraj plošče tako, da je tok skozi posamezen kristalizator podoben (največ do 100 L/min na mestu litja). Krmilni mehanizem z digitalno optično kodirno napravo za merjenje pomika plošče je montiran na nosilec livne plošče. Signal s kodirne naprave gre v posebno digitalno napravo, ki izračuna in prikaže trenutni položaj ter hitrost livne plošče. Naprava, ki jo regulira skrit priključek, ima hiter hidravlični bat in servomotor. Na ta način se zanesljivo doseže stabilna hitrost litja. Celotna naprava

Slika 1. Shema procesa nizkofrekvenčnega elektromagnetnega litja v napravi ELING LP-05 (1. peč, 2. odplinjevalna enota, 3. filter, 4. urejevalnik, 5. plošča litja, 6. energjska enota s sistemom krmilnega vodenja)

Figure 1. Scheme of LFEC process

was made in a casting device type ELING LP-05 (fig. 1,2). From the input point, the cast was distributed across the plate through ceramic channels, first to the central and then separately to each of the crystallizers.

The hot head on the crystallizers was also made of ceramics and had the role of maintaining the cast at a constant and stable temperature.

The hot head sits on a graphite ring, the orifice of which is smaller than the one of the crystallizer, to separate partially the cast in the warm head from the material in the crystallizers that was beginning to harden. The crystallizers were made of aluminum, with the upper part, where the most intensive contact with the molten metal is, having a graphite ring inserted that prevents local bonding of the material, and thereby positively affecting the quality of the surface of the billets.

The crystallizer is in one-piece, with the outer surface cooled by contact, and toward the output side along rim holes are drilled through which water flows, cooling in this way both the crystallizer and the billet.

An electromagnetic field is generated around the mold at the level of the graphite ring (fig. 2). The in-service stainless steel

Slika 2. Liv elektromagn
Figure 2. C an electrom

je priključena na osrednji računalniški sistem za avtomatizacijo procesa.

Pri vseh vzorcih za oba procesa je bila tekoča kovina pripravljena na enak način, imela je enako kemično sestavo, livni parametri so bili enaki, kar je omogočilo primerjalne analize. Pri obeh procesih litja je bil notranji premer kokile 178 mm, hitrost litja je bila 130 mm/min in livna temperatura 725 °C. Elektromagnetno polje je ustvarjalo 80 ovojev vodno hlajene bakrene tuljave okoli kristalizatorja iz nerjavnega jekla. Med ulivanjem je bila frekvenca nastavljena na 25 Hz in jakost toka je bila 85 A.

Drogovi, kokilno uliti z neposrednim hlajenjem, so bili po litju in strjevanju homogenizacijsko žarjeni 6 ur pri 570 °C, potem pa ohlajeni z ventilatorjem na sobno temperaturo. Drogovi, uliti v nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem polju, pa glede na namen raziskave niso bili homogenizacijsko žarjeni.

Preiskali smo makro- in mikrostrukture vzorcev zlitine 6060, ulite po klasičnem kokilnem postopku z dodatnim hlajenjem in po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem litju. Makro- in mikrostrukture so bile analizirane na prerezi vzorcev, ki so bili pripravljene po standardni metalografski metodi. Analizirani so bili na treh mestih

casting plate is completely under a pressure of about 2.5-5 bar. The casting plate has only one connection side for the inflow and the water is performed through each channel (max up to 100 L / min). A gear mechanism with an encoder to measure the rotation is mounted on the support. The signal from the encoder goes to a special digital device and displays the current speed of the casting plate. The speed is regulated by a retracting hydraulic piston. In this way, a stable casting speed is achieved. The whole device is controlled by a central PLC (central control automation of process).

All samples for both processes underwent the same preparation, had the same composition and the casting speed were the same, thus enabling comparative analyses to be performed. In both processes, the inner diameter was 178 mm, the casting speed was 130 mm / min and the casting temperature was 725 °C. The electro-

trdne raztopine α in intermetalnih faz so bili vzorci jedkani s Kellerjevim jedkalom. Za ovrednotenje mikrostrukture in ugotavljanje velikosti zrn se je uporabila svetlobna mikroskopija z mikroskopom Leica DM/RM. Za prepoznavanje intermetalnih faz je bila uporabljena EDS-analiza. Jedkanje s Truckerjevim jedkalom se je uporabilo za ugotavljanje velikosti in oblike zrn.

Natezne lastnosti so se merile po standardu UNI EN ISO 6892-1 # z univerzalnim merilnikom ZWICK Z150 in trdote po standardu UNI EN ISO 6506-1 # z napravo EMCO-TEST M4U 025. Za

a)

b)

Slika 4. Površina drogov pri a) litju z neposrednim hlajenjem, b)

the frequency was fixed at 25 Hz and the current intensity was 85 A.

The billets obtained by the DC process after casting and solidification were subjected to homogenization annealing at 570 °C for 6 hours, after which they were fan-cooled to room temperature. In accordance with the research aim, billets obtained by the LFEC procedure were not subjected to homogenization annealing.

The macro and microstructure of the 6060 alloy samples cast by the conventional DC and the LFEC process were examined. The macro and microstructures were studied in the cross section of the samples after the usual metallographic preparation. Analysis was performed at three points in the cross section: near the outer surface (edge), in the middle of the outer edge to the middle (D/4) and in the middle of billet (D/2). To determine the morphology of the distribution of the α -solid solution and intermetallic phases, etching was performed in Keller's reagent. Optical microscopy (LOM) was employed for the evaluation of the microstructure and determination of the grain size using a type Leica DM/RM microscope. While EDS analysis was used for the identification of the intermetallic phases. Etching by Trucker's reagent was used to determine the size and shape of the grains.

The measurements of the tensile properties were realized according to standard UNI EN ISO 6892-1 # on a universal testing machine ZWICK Z150 and the hardness standard UNI EN ISO 6506-1 # on an EMCO-TEST M4U 025 unit. Testing of mechanical properties was performed on test tubes extracted from the billets. All tests were performed at a room temperature of

merjenje mehanskih lastnosti so se iz drogov izdelali okrogli preizkušanci. Vsi preizkusi so potekali pri sobni temperaturi 22 °C.

Blokovno shemo poskusa kaže slika 3.

3 REZULTATI IN RAZPRAVA

3.1 Makroskopska analiza

Zunanjo obliko ulitih drogov iz zlitine 6060 kaže slika 4.

Površino drogov, ulitih s standardnim postopkom z neposrednim hlajenjem, kaže slika 4a, z nizkofrekvenčnim elektromagnetnim postopkom pa slika 4b, iz primerjave je očitna bolj groba površina pri standardnem postopku in bolj gladka pri nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku.

Slika 5 kaže makrostrukturo na prerezu vzorcev, ulitih po standardnem postopku (slika 5a) in po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku (slika 5b). Rezultati metalografskih preiskav kažejo, da je makrostruktura vzorcev, ulitih po standardnem postopku, sestavljena iz enakomerno razporejenih globulitov v sredini (slika 5c) in transkristalov po obodu (na sliki označeno z rdečimi puščicami). Makrostruktura vzorcev, ulitih po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku, vsebuje tudi drobne globulite v sredini, enakomerno razporejene po vsem prerezu razen v coni transkristalov, ki so v okoli 3 mm debelem pasu, kot je prikazano z rdečo puščico na sliki 5d.

3.2 Metalografska analiza

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Macroscopic analysis

The exterior configuratic alloy 6060 are shown in

The external surface by casting using the conv process is shown in fig. a billet obtained by casti process is illustrated in fig. it can be concluded that by the conventional DC have coarse external st obtained by the LFEC ca a smooth external surfac

Figure 5 shows a c macrostructure of the by the conventional DC (fig. 5a) and the LFEC The results of metalogr indicated that the sampl conventional DC casting to fine equiaxial grains, l with columnar shaped g red arrows in the figure dominated again by fine homogeneously distribu macrostructure of the s LFEC process, as in t was characterized by fir homogeneously distribu section, except for a grains extending in an a indicated by the red arro

3.2 Metallographic ana

Determination of grain s on the cross section of s both procedures, at the

Slika 5. Mikroposnetki prereza droga, narejeni s svetlobnim mikroskopom, povečava 0,5 x. Označena območja (rob, $d/4$ in sredina) predstavljajo mesta nadaljnjih preiskav: a) litje z neposrednim hlajenjem (DC), b) nizkofrekvenčno elektromagnetno litje (LFEC), c) sredina vzorca DC, d) robna cona vzorca LFEC)

Figure 5. Optical micrographs of the cross-section of a billet, magnification 0.5x. Marked areas (edge, $d/4$ and center) represent sites of further analysis: a) DC casting process; b) LFEC process; c) DC sample, center; d) LFEC sample, columnar zone.

Na vzorcih, ulitih po standardnem postopku, so bila zrna blizu roba globulitna. Pri eni analizi je bila opažena majhna razpoka (slika 7a). Blizu prehodne cone ($d/4$) so bili transkristali, medtem ko so v sredini zopet prevladovali enakomerni globuliti. V vzorcih, ulitih po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku, pa so bili globuliti po vsem prerezu, le na zunanjem robu je bil okoli 3 mm debel pas transkristalov. Pri obeh postopkih so bila najdrobnejša zrna na robu. To je razumljivo, saj je bilo ohlajanje na robu najhitrejše, ker je bil drog v neposrednem stiku s kristalizadorjem. Tam se navadno izločajo tudi nečistoče, ki predstavljajo potencialne kristalizacijske kleti. Na splošno so bila zrna v vzorcih ulitih

equal-axial. During one testing, a small crack was observed (fig. 7a). Near the transitional zone ($d/4$), there was columnar growth, while the center was again dominated by equiaxial and uniform grains. In the samples obtained by the LFEC process, the grains were equiaxial throughout the section, with columnar growth in a outer area of about 3 mm. Both procedures yielded the smallest grains along the edge. This is understandable since the edges experience the fastest cooling rate, *i.e.*, the billet is in direct contact with the crystallizer, and impurities are usually deposited there, which act as potential centers of crystallization. Generally, the grains in samples obtained by the LFEC casting

Slika 6. Svetlobni mikroposnetki mikrostrukture, 6x povečano (od leve proti desno): a) standardni postopek, b) nizkofrekvenčni elektromagnetni postopek

Figure 6. Optical micrographs of grain microstructure, 6x zoom (from left to right formed in: a) DC casting process; b) LFEC process

(slika 6a). Seveda to ni bila samo posledica uporabe električnih in magnetnih polj, ampak tudi posledica rekristalizacije zrn v vzorcih, ulitih po standardnem postopku, ker so bili ti drogovski rekristalizacijsko žarjeni, pri čemer so se raztopili dendriti, nastali med ohlajevanjem ulitka, kar je preoblikovalo podzrna v zrna in povzročilo njihovo rast itn. Vendar je učinek elektromagnetnega polja očiten.

Mikroposnetki na slikah 6 – 8 se od leve na desno nanašajo na rob (površina droga), na prehodno cono ($d/4$) in na sredino prereza

of the application of electric fields, but also due to grains in the samples obtained by the DC method, since these billets were not subjected to homogenization and dissolution of the dendrites (cooling after casting), sub-grains into grains, etc. Nevertheless, the effect of the electromagnetic field is clearly visible.

The photomicrographs from left to right refer to the surface, the transitional zone ($d/4$) and the center of the section.

Slika 7. Mikrostrukture označenih območij, povečava 50x (od leve proti desni: rob, d/4, sredina), a) standardni postopek litja, b) nizkofrekvenčni elektromagnetni postopek

Figure 7. Microstructure of the marked areas, 50x zoom (from left to right: edge, d/4, center): a) DC casting process; b) LFEC process

strani slike 6b, ki se nanaša na podrobnost transkristalov v prehodni coni (d/4).

Mikrostrukture vzorcev, ulitih po standardnem in nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku, kažeta pri povečavi 50 x sliki 7a in 7b.

Mikrostrukture vzorcev, ulitih po standardnem in nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku kažeta pri povečavi 500 x sliki 8a in 8b.

V vzorcu, ulitem po standardnem postopku, je bila mikrostruktura sestavljena iz α -aluminija, na katerega kristalnih mejah so bile naključno porazdeljene intermetalne

to a detail within the columnar grains in the transitional zone (d/4).

The microstructures of the samples obtained by the DC casting process and the LFEC process at 50x zoom are shown in figure 7a and b, respectively.

The microstructures of the samples obtained in the conventional DC casting process and the LFEC process at 500x zoom are shown in figure 8a and b, respectively.

For the sample obtained by the DC process, the microstructure consists of α -aluminum having at the grain boundaries randomly assigned intermetallic phases,

Slika 8. Mikrostrukture označenih območij, povečava 500x (od leve proti desni: standardni postopek litja, b) nizkofrekvenčni elektromagnetni postopek

Figure 8. Microstructure of the marked areas, 500x zoom (from left to right: edge, casting process; b) LFEC process

3). Ostali mikrodelci kroglaste oblike so rezultat pretvorbe ploščičaste monoklinske β -faze v okroglo kubično α -fazo pri homogenizacijskem žarjenju.

Tudi za prehodno cono (d/4) je značilna prisotnost intermetalnih faz v α -aluminiju, deloma razporejenih po kristalnih mejah. Prisotnost okroglih delcev je tu še bolj očitna (slika 8a). To območje ni bilo analizirano z EDS. Predpostavlja se, da je poleg zrn α -aluminija prisotna še faza Mg_2Si .

Mikrostruktura v sredini je podobna tisti v prehodni coni, vendar je ploščičasta β -faza nekoliko tanjša in manj očitna (slika

9a, 10a, tables 2 and 3). particles, present in the are the result of transition solid, plate-like, monoclinic α -phase homogenization annealing

The transitional zone is characterized by the intermetallic phases in fragments arranged by the The presence of globular more visible here (fig. 8 of this area were not possible to be assumed that in a

Glede mikrostrukture vzorcev, ulitih nizkofrekvenčno elektromagnetno se lahko na splošno ugotavlja naslednje:

V robni površinski plasti, debeli okoli 200 μm so bile na mejah zrn, ki segajo na razdalji okoli 1,5 mm proti sredini, prisotne zelo ploščate kepice intermetalnih faz. Verjetno so prisotne znatne količine β -faze (sliki 7, 8). Rezultati EDS-analize so pokazali, da so te spojine vrste AlSiFe . Občasno prisotni ostali okrogli delci se nanašajo na fazo Mg_2Si (slika 9b, razpredelnica 2).

Za prehodno cono (d/4) je značilen α -aluminij z intermetalnimi prednostno

plate-like β -phase is somewhat thinner and less visible (fig. 8a). The globular particles present are the product of both, β - α transformation and the presence of Mg_2Si phases, as indicated by the results of EDS analysis of the center of the billet (fig. 10a, table 3).

For the microstructure of the samples cast by the LFEC procedure, the following can generally be stated:

In the surface (bordering) layer, to a depth of about 200 μm , strong plate-like nubs of intermetallic compounds are present at the grain boundaries, which

Slika 9. Slike povratno sipanih elektronov blizu roba vzorca in ustreznih EDS-analiz: a) ulito po standardnem postopku, b) ulito po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku. Označena mesta

Razpredelnica 2. EDS-mikroanalize v površinski coni

Table 2. EDS microanalysis at surface section,

mesto / location	standardni postopek litja / conventional DC casting process					vsota / Total	nizkofrekvenčno elekt LFEC prc			
	C	Al	Si	Fe	Ni		Mg	Al	Si	Ca
1	14,22	56,23	4,44	17,26	7,85	100,00	0,69	78,54	4,72	
2	16,05	76,08	2,95	4,92		100,00		75,95	7,19	
3		100,00				100,00		100		
4	13,43	86,57				100,00	5,15	64,66	11,02	0,55

Vsi rezultati so v mas. % / All results are in weight %.

usmerjenimi fazami. Ker ni bilo difuzije (drogovi, uliti po tem postopku, niso bili homogenizacijsko žarjeni), je bilo prisotnih večje število okroglih delcev faze Mg_2Si . Prisotne ploščicaste intermetalne faze so bile drobnejše kot v vzorcih, ulitih po standardnem postopku (sliki 7 in 8).

V sredini vzorca so bile tanke ploščicaste faze prisotne na mejah zrn α -aluminija z občasno prisotnostjo ostalih okroglih mikrodolcev (sliki 7, 8).

SEM-posnetki površine drogov, ulitih po obeh postopkih, so na sliki 9. Na sliki so označena območja, ki so bila analizirana z EDS za ugotavljanje elementne sestave. V drogu, ulitem po standardnem postopku (slika 9a, razpredelnica 2), so se občasno pojavljale ploščicaste in iglaste faze β - AlSiFe ob občasni prisotnosti skepljene α - AlSiFe intermetalne faze, medtem ko je bila v drogu, ulitem po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku (slika 9b, razpredelnica 2), bolj izrazita prisotnost intermetalne faze β - AlSiFe z občasno prisotnostjo faze Mg_2Si .

SEM-posnetke sredin drogov, ulitih po obeh postopkih, kaže slika 10. Na sliki so označena mesta EDS-analiz. V drogu, ulitem po standardnem postopku, so v mikrostrukturi vidne debele ploščicaste

extend toward the center 1.5 mm. It is probable amounts of β -phase are The results of EDS an these are compounds The sporadically preser residue refer to Mg_2Si table 2).

The transitional characterized by α -al intermetallic phases grain boundary in a pr Due to the absence billets cast by this subjected to homogen a more pronounced n of MgSi phase are pres intermetallic phases pre thinner than those in th the standard procedure

In the center of the like intermetallic phases α -aluminum at grain b sporadic presence of g micro-residue (fig. 7, 8).

SEM images of tl billets cast by both proc figure 9. The locations \ where recorded to deter composition are marke

Slika 10. Slike sredine, narejene s povratno sipanimi elektroni, in ustrezne EDS-analize: a) standardni postopek litja, b) ulito po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku. Označena so mesta EDS-mikroanaliz

Figure 10. Back scattered electron images of the central section (D/2) of the of the specimens and corresponding EDS spectra : a) DC casting process, b) LFEC process. Marked points correspond to the sites of EDS microanalysis

Razpredelnica 3. EDS-mikroanalize v sredini (D/2)

Table 3. EDS microanalysis in the center (D/2)

mesto / location	standardni postopek litja / conventional DC casting process						ulito po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku / LFEC process							
	O	Mg	Al	Si	Fe	Vsota / Total	C	O	Mg	Al	Si	Ca	Fe	Vsota / Total
1	12,00	1,87	77,88	8,25		100,00	19,88	18,72	1,89	47,63	11,56	0,32		100,00
2	41,52	3,58	39,18	13,86	1,86	100,00	27,48	7,11	1,16	60,17	3,74	0,35		100,00
3						100,00	20,85		0,54	73,61	2,92		2,09	100,00

Vse vrednosti so v mas. % / All results are in weight %.

Razpredelnica 4. Mehanske lastnosti

Table 4. Mechanical properties

mesto vzorčenja / place of sampling	Rp _{0,2} N/mm ²	Rm N/mm ²	A %	Z %	HBW 2,5/31,2
1LFEC-e	57	141	33,0	57,3	39-39-41
2LFEC-d/4	54	142	31,0	60,3	42-44-44
3LFEC-sredina	54	144	29,0	59,4	43-44-43
1DC-e	57	147	26,0	53,8	43-44-43
2DC-d/4	54	145	29,0	52,8	43-45-44
3DC-sredina	54	146	29,0	57,3	43-43-43

kristalnih zrn mnogo tanjše in manj vidne. Prisotni pa so tudi delci Mg₂Si (slika 10b, razpredelnica 3).

2.3 Mehanske lastnosti

Rezultate mehanskih preskusov vzorcev, ki so bili vzeti na mestih, označenih na sliki 5b, prikazuje razpredelnica 4.

Rezultati mehanskih preskusov ne kažejo pri nateznih lastnostih (napetost tečenja, natezna trdnost) razlike med obema postopkoma, medtem ko so plastičnostne značilnosti (raztezek in skrček) nekoliko višje pri vzorcih, ulitih po nizkofrekvenčnem elektromagnetnem postopku. Razlike pri vrednostih trdot so zanemarljive. Nizke vrednosti natezne trdnosti in visoke vrednosti plastičnosti (raztezek in skrček) so bile pričakovane, ker material ni bil toplotno obdelan po nobenem postopku (T5 ali T6), ki se navadno zahteva med iztiskovanjem (T5) ali po njem (T6).

4 SKLEPI

Na osnovi preiskave vzorcev, ulitih po standardnem postopku z neposrednim

by the LFEC process shows the expressed AlFeSi intermetallic phase presence of the Mg₂Si phase. SEM images of the billets cast by both processes (figure 10). The locations were recorded to determine composition are marked. In the billet obtained by the LFEC process strong plate phases, consisting mainly of the sporadic presence of the intermetallic phase are visible at the grain boundaries (table 3). In the billet obtained by the DC process, the intermetallic phase grain boundaries are much more visible. In addition, plate phases are present (figure 11).

3.3. Mechanical properties

Test results of mechanical samples taken from the specimens (figure 5b) are shown in table 4.

The results of the tensile tests show no significant differences in tensile properties (yield strength) of the samples cast by these two methods, while the plasticity (elongation) values were slightly higher in the samples cast by the LFEC process. Differences in yield strength were not significant. Low yield strength and high plasticity (elongation and contraction) were expected, as the material had not been subjected to any thermal treatment (T5) or after (T6) extrusion.

- mikrostrukture drogov, ulitih po obeh postopkih, so zelo podobne. Vendar je mikrostruktura, dobljena z nizkofrekvenčnim elektromagnetnim litjem, bolj drobnozrnata, čistejša so površine drogov in drobnejše ter manj vidne so intermetalne faze na kristalnih mejah v sredini drogov in v prehodnih conah, kar je zanesljivo pomembno za nadaljnje predelovanje. Intermetalne faze blizu površine so pri tem postopku nekoliko bolj vidne kot pri standardnem postopku;
- mehanske lastnosti pri obeh vrstah vzorcev so bile skoraj identične, kar je druga dobra stran nizkofrekvenčnega elektromagnetnega litja;
- uporaba nizkofrekvenčnega elektromagnetnega litja brez dolgotrajnega in dragega homogenizacijskega žarjenja daje enak učinek kot standardno litje s homogenizacijo. Zato ta postopek omogoča občutno skrajšanje cikla in največje prihranke z vidika trajanja homogenizacije. To bi tudi prispevalo k znatnemu zmanjšanju stroškov dela in energije ter s tem zmanjšalo ceno končnega izdelka;
- uporaba elektro-magnetnih polj pri ulivanju aluminijevih drogov predstavlja pot za širšo uporabo te tehnologije, čeprav jo je treba še skrbno preučiti in uporabiti v industrijskih razmerah. Dobljeni rezultati se lahko uporabijo za nadaljnji razvoj in izboljšave procesa predvsem za litje trdih zlitin vrste 2xxx in zlitin s povečano trdnostjo vrste 7xxx kot tudi drugih zlitin za ulivanje drogov in ploščatih blokov.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of results of experimental testing of samples obtained by the conventional direct chill (DC) casting process and the LFEC process, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The microstructures of the cast billets obtained by both procedures were very similar. Yet, application of the LFEC procedure results in finer grains, cleaner surfaces of the billet and finer and less visible intermetallic phases at the grain boundaries, in the center and the transition zone of billet, which are certainly of importance for further processing. Near the surface, the intermetallic phases present were slightly more visible compared to those obtained using the conventional DC process.
- Mechanical properties of both types of samples were almost identical, which is another upside for the LFEC procedure.
- By using the LFEC process without the lengthy and expensive process of homogenization annealing, the same effect can be achieved as by the conventional DC process with homogenization annealing. This enables the possibility of significant shortening, even the maximal savings in the duration of homogenization annealing in this type of alloy. This would also contribute to a significant reduction of the consumption of work and energy, resulting in reduced cost of the finished product.
- The application of electromagnetic fields during the casting of aluminum billets is the way towards a wider application

republike Srbije preko evropskega projekta EUREKA 6735! ESPAL (<http://www.eurekanetwork.org/project/-/id/6735>) in za pomoč ter sodelovanje upravam in delovnim skupinam v podjetjih Eling, Loznica (www.eling.rs) ter Deral, Brescia, Italija (www.deral.it). Zahvaljujejo se tudi dr. Tamari Radetić z Univerze Beograd za pomoč pri pripravi tega prispevka (tradetic@tmf.bg.ac.rs).

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obtained results of further development of the process, application of hardening and alloys with elevated strength, as well as other aspects of the manufacture of

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AKTUALNO / ACTUAL

Nemški livarski dan 2013 s 5. NEWCAST-forumom

Na povabilo VDG-Društva nemških livarjev smo se udeležili osrednjega livarskega dogodka v Nemčiji pod naslovom »Deutschen Giessereitag 2013 s 5. NEWCAST-forumom, ki

je potekal v času o 2013 v Fellbachu pri S je sodelovalo več kol V dveh dneh je bil strokovnih predava razvoju v livarski Aktualne razmere v l bile predstavljene kar predavanji.

Prvi plenarni Steinheider, predse Deutscher Giesse poudaril, da prihodnos jutri ne bo z ljudmi c livarska panoga se vodi novo kampanjo, strokovnjakov pres

pomlajenimi kadri. Poudaril je, da je nemška livarska panoga danes vodilnih livarskih narodov, ker obvladujejo moderne proizvodne post gospodarske livarske rešitve. Zaključil je, da Nemčija samo z zelo c strokovnjaki lahko ohrani ta vrhunski položaj.

Drugi plenarni predavatelj, Willi Fuchs, direktor in član preds Deutscher Ingenieure, si je uvodoma zastavil vprašanje, ali proizvodn sploh ima prihodnost? Menil je, da so tudi v prihodnje inovacije ključ za c Tudi v pogojih obstoja nadaljnje rasti globalizacije so po njegovem m pogoji, da se nadalje dograjuje tehnološko vrhunski položaj nemške liv

Tretji plenarni predavatelj, dr. ing. Erwin Flender, predsednik BGI der Deutschen Giesserei-Industrienje, je podal podroben pogled sta nemške livarske industrije. V zaključku pa je skiciral temelje nove komun BDG. Z novo spletno stranjo www.guss.de se predstavljajo kot moder usmerjeno nemško združenje, za katerega se ni bati, da bi ga ne smeli p panogami. Dr. Flender je usmeril svoj pogled tudi na konjunktorni razvc Njegov pogled na drugo polovico leta 2013 je bil rahlo optimističen.

Nemške livarne so v mednarodnem konkurenčnem okolju dobre razpolagajo z znatnim »Know-how« prednostmi. V ospredju so bile re energije, povečanju cen surovin, kot tudi naprej o »Hightech-produktih«, l iz litine na proizvodni lokaciji Nemčije.

Spremljajoča razstava NEW CAST-foruma »Konstruiranje z livar je bila usmerjena na konstrukterje in na nabavnike livarskih izdelkov. razstavnimi izdelki nazorno pokazala, kako pomembni so uliti ugradr zahtevam, ki izhajajo iz želje po mobilnosti, zanesljivi energetski osl realizaciji.

Zainteresiranim udeležencem so bile predstavljene trenutne tehnič